

THE IMPORTANCE OF FAMILIARIZING STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS WITH FICTION

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"The book (bitig) is the basis of all creativity, creativity and intelligence, knowledge and wisdom, the creator of life is the coach"

Emir Temur

Annotation. Fiction - not only gives a person knowledge, education, education, but also psychologically develops him, provides great help in the development of speech, vocabulary replenishment, strengthening sociability

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As the great poet and thinker Alisher Navoi wrote, "The book is the main source of achieving mastery, knowledge and spiritual growth," and the great Russian poet M. Gorky wrote that "I am grateful to the book for all the good qualities that I possess."

In fact, the book is considered the best friend for a person. Among our people you can find many things, such as "craft is a source of current, science is a burning lamp", "mind is a wingless bird without a book", "knowledge is a lamp of the mind", "Golden apple, get knowledge, get knowledge, learn", "beauty is science in enlightenment", "knowledge is a sign of happiness", "science brings happiness, brings the throne of knowledge".

An important factor for a person to be educated, professional and, of course, happy and wealthy is friendship with a book, and not constant reading and reading books for life. Because a good book brings up in a person a sense of love for the Motherland, respect for national and universal values, encourages good

As you know, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev dated January 12, 2017 “On the establishment of a commission for the development of the system of printing and distribution of book products, improving and promoting the culture of reading and reading” is extremely important because it is aimed at raising this noble cause to a new, higher level.

In fact, the earlier the child's speech manifests, the earlier his mental development and expansion of thinking occur, the earlier his abilities manifest themselves. Experiments show that the earlier the child's language comes out, the larger the vocabulary, the stronger the educational and cognitive activity of the child at school is manifested. It is in this process that the more a child gets acquainted with fiction from adults, the greater his rapprochement with fiction directly leads to the development of their speech, the formation of memory and thinking, and the enrichment of vocabulary.

On the other hand, a person reflects events and phenomena throughout the objective world with the help of various sensory analyzers in his mind and manifests them in his speech.

Increasing the motivation of students of higher educational institutions to read, the formation of a reading culture is considered today as the most urgent issue. But do all students have the same passion for reading? At this stage, it is also very important that they clearly define what they are reading, for example, reading. What benefits do books for reading bring to a person? Can they add new knowledge? can he help direct our efforts for the better and give us inner peace, pleasure from work?

Mark Twain explains that "there is no difference between a person who does not like a good book, educated and ignorant," emphasizing the importance of a good book.

The least useful book is harmful only because it wastes time. A book that leads a person to laziness, unemployment, immorality and unbelief is no different from poison. Such books turn the material and spiritual life of people into chaos.

Just as we choose the useful, the good in everything, the choice of the best and useful books for students determines the main direction in their lives. A person's worldview

is formed through books. If the student can choose a good one, the book will become his best friend and brother. This teaches us to strive to always be close to loyal friends. Remember that there is no other treasure except the book.

Books are sources that don't lose people. People who have not polished their minds with a book, who do not feed their souls with it, cannot get rid of boredom, boredom. Seneca did not say for nothing: "to live without a book is to live like a blind, deaf, mute."

The great scientist, Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf Hazrat, based on his experience and recommendations for reading books, gave the following recommendations:

1. Keeping a diary for reading books. At the same time, every time you start a book, this day is recorded in a notebook.

2. Even for sentences that you can't understand in the book, keep taking notes in a notebook. When you can't understand a word or sentence, you shouldn't waste time, from time to time a simple expressive form of this word or sentence pops up from somewhere. It is then that the riddle that torments you will be solved by itself.

3. Setting the end date of the book. Then you will be able to see how many and what books you have read. This pose will give you more courage.

4. In every job you need to be organized and firmly adhere to the tasks set. When you struggle to force yourself to do something, it becomes a constant state of affairs for you. The main thing is that the person who read the book today is different from yesterday.

"Nowadays, people are used to reading long information on phones and similar devices. However, in this, too, you can get a lot of knowledge. But the role of the book is different. In the book, the author first writes a preface. It sets out what topic and what is being discussed in this work. Then he starts the conversation with the history of the subject he is covering, and gradually reaches the main point. Then he makes his word, making the necessary conclusions. Therefore, between a person who reads a book from the outside and a person who reads information from this

earth, there will be a difference between Earth and heaven, if you say something, he will not be able to think comprehensively,” Sheikh Hazrat emphasizes.

Studies have revealed the following benefits of reading for a person:

1. Reading helps to get rid of insomnia.
2. Reading calms the nerves.
3. Reading softens the soul.
4. Reading improves brain function.
5. Reading helps fight depression.
6. Reading makes a person more beautiful.
7. Reading improves memory and thinking skills.
8. Reading helps to realize your purpose in life and overcome difficulties.
9. Reading increases vocabulary.
10. People who read books are active in life.
11. Reading develops writing skills.
12. Reading can prevent Alzheimer's disease.
13. Reading makes learning a foreign language easier.
14. Reading develops the ability to be creative.
15. Reading helps to cope with financial difficulties.
16. Reading together improves parent-child interaction.
17. Children who read a lot of books learn lessons better.
18. Reading prevents crime.
19. Reading develops the ability to listen.
20. Reading makes a good storyteller.
21. Reading encourages doing good

Therefore, teaching students of higher educational institutions (future teachers) friendship with the book is an important factor in their further development as excellent teachers. This will serve to ensure the rise, prosperity and bright future of the Uzbek state.

According to the definition of the outstanding Uzbek writer Oybek, a book is a tolerant wing of thought. In this sense, we can say that the book is the pearl of the

human soul, the treasure of contemplation. We must ensure that the book is the most priceless gift for our children. Only then will our children grow up to be what we dream of, spiritually mature, capable of thinking deeply, kind to big and small, loyal to their homeland, honest, loyal and noble people.

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